

MODERN COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY IN DENTISTRY**Magistrs: Rashidova Nozima Uktam Kizi****Tillakhujayeva Diyora Otabek Kizi****Tashkent State Dental Institute****Department of surgical dentistry and orthopedics, masters' degree, 1st semester****Juan Rapheal Diaz Simoes****Scientific Supervisor: Associate Professor of the Department of Biophysics and
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Abstract: modern computer modeling and prosthetic manufacturing systems are finding Widely used in dentistry. This is due to the possibility of reducing the stages of prosthetics, the use of new aesthetic and durable materials, and the high level of their processing. All systems for computer modeling and manufacturing of prostheses consist of three main functional components: modules for scanning, design, and automated manufacturing. Main stages manufacturing dental restorations using computer technology are: obtaining digital impression, processing and transformation of the received digital information, reconstruction of the surface of the teeth on the monitor, construction of a virtual model of the future restoration, automated production of restoration. All existing systems for computer modeling and production of prostheses are differentiated mainly by the type of three-dimensional data collection on the geometry of the oral cavity, by the range of manufactured denture designs and the structural materials used, and also on the business model of use in the clinic. A significant role in the popularization of technology is played by transition from a two-dimensional image to isometry, which allows visualization and control in the full process of designing a restoration on a monitor screen, as well as the emergence of new structural materials that combine the aesthetics of ceramics and the strength of metal.

Key words: CAD/CAM systems, dentistry, dentures.

Possibilities for their use in dentistry at all stages of patient treatment include maintaining medical records, diagnostics (radiovisiographs, computed tomographs, virtual articulators, digital photographic equipment), modeling and simulation of clinical situations, treatment. Methods are being developed for obtaining and orienting three-dimensional computer models of teeth and dental rows, measuring the height of fissures, cusps, the shape of their slopes, methods of controlling odontopreparation [4,5]. One of the symbols of the innovative development of dentistry in recent years is the technology of computer design and manufacture of prostheses, for which there is a generally accepted designation abbreviation – CAD/CAM. The development of automated production systems in industry began in the 60s of the 20th century [10]. At the same time, basic concepts and classification began to form systems and subsystems according to their target characteristics. According to GOST 34.003-90 and GOST standards 23501.101-87 computer-aided design system, CAD – an automated system that implements information technology to perform design functions. The main The goal and objectives of creating CAD systems are to increase labor efficiency, including: reducing

the labor intensity of design and planning; reduction of design time; reduction in design and manufacturing costs, reduction in operating costs; improving quality and technical and economic level of design results; reduction in modeling and testing costs. CAD/CAM technologies are a special example of CAD. CAD (English computer-aided design/drafting) - computer-aided design tools, CAM (English computer-aided manufacturing) - means of technological preparation for the production of products [6,7]. An adequate analogue of the English abbreviation CAD/CAM in relation to dentistry is: systems for computeraided design and automated manufacturing of restorations. Since CAD was already actively used in manufacturing in the early 80s, it was believed that CAD/CAM systems for dental purposes will be a simplified version of industrial ones. However, in reality, the production of dental CAD/CAM systems was not neither simple nor easy for a number of reasons. The total cost, operating time and quality of the final product produced by CAD/CAM systems should be on par with traditional methods, and The ideal is to surpass them in all respects in order to replace them in everyday laboratory and clinical practice. The morphology of the supporting teeth, as well as adjacent and antagonist teeth, must be accurately digitized to create high-quality restorations. However, it was quite difficult to recognize subtle edges of prepared teeth using scanners available at that time. Thus, the development of accurate and compact scanners and associated software was necessary for accomplish this complex and delicate task. Moreover, since restoration should not only be adapted along the preparation line, but also to harmonize with natural teeth, as well as restore occlusal contact, requires complex CAD software. Accurate is required, but delicate mechanical processing of fragile ceramic materials, taking into account complex geometrical forms of restorations, which requires the use of high-quality CAM equipment with software to control the trajectory and feed speed of the tool. In addition, the dimensions of the processing units must be limited to installation in a standard dental office or laboratory [eleven]. Finally, unlike the mass production of industrial parts, each restoration is individual and unique. Consequently, the specific amount of time and intellectual costs is incomparably greater. However, despite the above difficulties, CAD/CAM systems have gradually found acceptance in the dental community. The capabilities of modern CAD/CAM systems are the result of a long evolution that has not yet been reached its peak. The development of dental systems began at the end of the 70s of the 20th century. The developers set the following tasks: - to standardize the process of designing restorations, to minimize the subjective human factor, giving a clear digital expression to the modeling parameters; - improve and unify dental structural materials by using standard blanks; - reduce time and labor costs for the manufacture of dental restorations.

Several pioneer systems that made the first significant contribution to the development of CAD/CAM technologies in dentistry are considered the recognized ancestors. In the literature there is information about developers from the USA JMYoung and BR Altschuler, who made theoretical calculations about the use of laser holographic optics to display the surface of teeth Francois Duret was the first

practitioner in the field of dental CAD/CAM. Since 1971, he began working on a project capable of produce crowns with a functional form of the chewing surface. The scan was based

based on the principle of laser holographic optics. The crowns were designed taking into account functional movements and were milled using a computer numerical control machine. For the production of one restoration took about four hours. The first prototype of the Duret system was presented at the Entretiens Garancieres conference in France in 1983. Sopha Duret later became the Sopha Bioconcept ® system. The system did not find wide acceptance due to the complexity of all operations performed and high cost, but it had an impact on the subsequent development of dental CAD/CAM systems in the world [10].

According to the above-mentioned modules of CAD/CAM systems, the main stages of manufacturing matological restorations using computer technology are:

- obtaining a digital impression, which is a registration of a complex of digital parameters of objects of interest to us. Depending on the volume and complexity of the restoration, these may be cavities prepared for inlays, stumps from prepared teeth, adjacent teeth, antagonist teeth. For this purpose, scanners or digitizers are used that use contact and non-contact methods for measuring the surface profile;
- processing and transformation of the obtained digital information, reconstruction of the surface of the teeth on the monitor, constructing a virtual model of the future restoration;
- automated production of restorations. The main modules of CAD/CAM systems correspond to the stages being produced, although sometimes they may be combined into one block.

The stages of manufacturing restorations differ in the so-called CAM systems, where there is no program for modeling a virtual restoration. This function is traditionally performed by a technician in a dental laboratory using wax, plastics, or other auxiliary materials. Subsequently, a replica restoration is scanned or immediately copied, embodied in construction material.

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